

Length Weight relationship of Terapon jarbua (Forsskal, 1775) from Puducherry waters

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Abstract : The present study investigates the length-weight relationship of Terapon jarbua from Puducherry (East coast of India). A total of 370 individuals of different sizes were collected from Puducherry landings centre. Length-weight relationships were calculated for all specimens sampled. The length weight relationship equations are $W = 0.0050 L^{3.2742}$; $W = 0.0035 L^{3.3616}$; $W = 0.0736 L^{2.4076}$; $W = 0.0098 L^{3.0807}$; $W = 0.0088 L^{3.0914}$; $W = 0.0038 L^{3.3776}$ for immature male, immature female, matured male, matured female, total male and total female respectively. The growth exponential (b) values were found to be positively allometric for all the stages except matured male.

Keywords : Allometry, Length weight relationship, Puducherry waters, Terapon jarbua.

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